

Housing impacts social connections for asylum-seekers and refugees in Oxfordshire

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Introduction

- Conditions in UK asylum-seeker accommodation are so unsafe that international aid organisations have staged interventions.
- Political controversy surrounds asylum hotels.
- Charities report systemic failures in housing this group.
- News reports of attacks on hotels showed that asylum-seekers living there are marginalised, whereas hosted refugees are integrated into communities.
- This research examines how different forms of accommodation foster or hinder social connectedness, addressing a gap in the literature and contributing evidence that could inform policy in the UK and beyond.

Conclusion

- Hosting supports autonomy and connection, and hotels and mass accommodation create isolation.
- Military accommodation in Oxfordshire provides cultural exchange and community integration.
- Ukrainian refugees are regularly housed in hotels after hosting, contrary to rhetoric about hotel-dwellers.
- Volunteering and shared activities create belonging.
- The findings highlight examples of public hostility and generosity, and how housing plays a crucial role in shaping social connections.

Methods

- Gathered opinion from professionals on prescient topics.
- Literature Review.
- Interviewed 13 professionals and volunteers supporting asylum-seekers and refugees in barracks, hosting and hotels in Oxfordshire.
- Completed thematic analysis.
- Compared the themes emerging from interviews with those in the literature.

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Recommendations

- Educate the public about asylum-seekers and refugees.
- Invest in mental health, communication and transport.
- Allow asylum-seekers to work or volunteer while awaiting decisions to reduce isolation, support wellbeing, and strengthen community connections.
- Develop planned, community-based resettlement for all asylum-seekers to promote inclusion, reduce discrimination, and improve coordination across councils.
- Reform asylum housing by replacing harmful mass accommodation and addressing the wider UK housing crisis through equitable, non-discriminatory policies.
- Expand hosting nationally with strong safeguarding, training, and monitoring.
- Challenge gender bias through positive public narratives.

Literature Review

- Structural violence explains the lack of access to housing for asylum-seekers, refugees, and poorer British communities.
- Expensive hotels and mass accommodation expose residents to greater vulnerability, mental illness.
- Community resentment increases due to poor communication between central and local government.
- Temporary housing shapes social connections for asylum-seekers and refugees in Oxfordshire.
- Hosting schemes offer the most autonomy and well-being but expanding them requires the government to abandon divisive and racialised rhetoric.
- There is an urgent need for humane temporary housing that supports social connection.
- There is a heavy reliance on the third sector.

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